

MECHANICAL, SHAPE MEMORY AND ANTIBACTERIAL PROPERTIES OF GRAPHENE OXIDE/PLLA NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) was grafted onto the graphene oxide surface to improve its dispersity in the polymer matrix. The modified graphene oxide (g-GO) was dispersed in the PLLA matrix by solution blending to prepare g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites with different compositions. Their structure, mechanical properties, shape memory properties and antibacterial properties are investigated by FTIR, DSC, SEM, tensile test and antibacterial experiment. As the g-GO content increases, the crystallinity of the g-GO/PLLA composite slightly decreases. The elastic modulus and tensile strength of the nanocomposites increases with the increase of g-GO content and when the g-GO loading is 1.0 wt%, the maximum can be obtained. However, the elongation at break is weakened by the addition of g-GO. The g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites show good shape memory effect and antibacterial properties. The enhanced mechanical properties together with shape memory properties and antibacterial properties arising from the introduction of g-GO suggest that these nanocomposites may potentially be useful for a variety of biomedical applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Poly(L-lactide) (PLLA) is one of the most important biodegradable polymers and has been widely used in various biomedical applications such as surgical sutures, bone fixation, tissue engineering and drug delivery systems because of its good mechanical properties, biodegradability and biocompatibility [1-3]. Recently, it is found that the PLLA has shape memory effect, which opens up new perspective for minimally invasive surgery [4,5]. Nevertheless, the mechanical and shape memory properties of this polymers need to be improved for special high performance applications. Moreover, the lack of biological functionality also limits its biomedical applications. To address this issue, a variety of strategies have been developed and the most direct and effective method is incorporation inorganic filler to make composites [6,7]. Graphene oxide (GO) is the material with superior mechanical, electrical and many functions such as cell imaging [8], drug loading [9], antibacterial and tumor therapy [10] in biomedicine. Thus, GO usually be applied as a reinforcing materials in polymers. However, the properties of nanocomposites are closely associated with homogeneous dispersion of the GO in polymer and the interfacial adhesion between the GO and the polymer matrix. However, to improve the dispersion of GO in polymer matrix is also be a difficult issue.

In this paper, GO is surface-grafted by direct polymerization of L-lactic acid. The resulting g-GO is incorporated in PLLA polymer matrix at different compositions. The microstructure, mechanical properties, shape memory properties and antibacterial properties of the GO/PLLA nanocomposites are investigated. These nanocomposites possess multiple functions such as shape memory effect, biodegradability and antibacterial properties. It is expected that these nanocomposites can be potentially used as implants for minimally invasive surgery.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

PLLA with molecular weight approximately 180,000 g/mol was synthesized according to the procedures in our previous study [5]. L-lactic acid (pharmaceutical grade) was purchased from Aladdin reagent Co., Ltd. Stannous octoate were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. Other chemical reagents were purchased from Tianjin Reagents and used as received.

2.2 Surface modification of graphene oxide

The surface modification of GO was carried out by the L-lactic acid solution polymerization method. Unmodified GO is dissolved in tetrahydrofuran at a ratio of 1 ml/mg, and then was sonicated for 2.5 h to obtain a homogenous GO suspension. The free water in L-lactic acid is removed by the principle of vacuum distillation. Dehydrated L-lactic acid (100ml) was mixed with GO tetrahydrofuran solution (75ml) in a three-necked flask under vigorous stirring for 2 h. Then stannous octoate as a catalyst (the amount of catalyst is 0.5wt% of L-lactic acid) was added into the mixture. After that, the three-mouth bottle placed on a magnetic stirrer, evacuated and gradually warmed to 150°C, continue to react for 5 hours. The reaction product was ultrasonically washed with dichloromethane and sedimented by centrifugation, and repeated four times. Finally, the centrifuge tube containing the g-GO was placed in a vacuum drying oven at 40°C and dried for 24 hours.

2.3 Preparation g-GO/PLCL nanocomposites

The g-GO/PLCL nanocomposites films was prepared by solution blending. Briefly, 10wt% of PLCL was dissolved in dichloromethane solution and stirred 2h at temperature until well mixed. Different concentrations of g-GO were dissolved in methylene chloride solvent in a proportion of 1mg/ml, and then they were completely dispersed by ultrasonic vibration to form a uniform and stable solution. After that, the g-GO dissolved in dichloromethane solution was gradually poured into the polymer-dissolved methylene chloride solution, subsequently stirring for 2h with sealing. Finally, the dichloromethane in the mixed solution is completely volatilized, and the composite film was formed and then was dried under vacuum at 40°C for 48h in order to remove all remaining dichloromethane.

2.4 Characterization

FTIR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum one spectrophotometer in the range of 4000 to 560 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 16 scans.

DSC analysis was performed on a PerkinElmer Diamond DSC instrument at a heating rate of 10°C/min from 0°C to 200°C. The degree of crystallinity was calculated from the measured heat of melting, using the value of heat of melting of the crystallinity regions of PLLA $\Delta H_m=93.1\text{J/g}$ taken from the reference [11].

The phase morphology of the PLLA/PLAL blends was observed by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL, JSM-6480A). The blend samples were dropped directly into liquid nitrogen and fractured to obtain fresh brittle failure surfaces. All failure surfaces were sputtered with gold before SEM observation.

The phase morphology of the g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites was observed by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL, JSM-6480A). The nanocomposites samples were dropped directly into liquid nitrogen and fractured to obtain fresh brittle failure surfaces. All failure surfaces were sputtered with gold before SEM observation.

2.5 Mechanical properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

The tensile tests were conducted on an Instron 3365 with a loading rate of 10mm/min at room temperature and 70 °C. Dumbbell shaped samples have effective dimensions of 16×4×0.3 mm³. All the experimental data were obtained from the average value of three samples for each blend.

2.6 Shape memory properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

Shape memory properties of PLLA/PLAL blends were investigated by the tensile test. The test procedure included four steps: (1) applying a deformation ($\varepsilon_m=100\%$) to the sample at a constant crosshead speed of 10mm/min at 70°C, (2) cooling the sample to 25°C while keeping $\varepsilon_m=100\%$ for 10 min, (3) removing the load, and (4) raising the temperature to 70°C and maintaining for 10 min. Under these conditions, shape retention ratio (R_f) and shape recovery ratio (R_r) are defined as follows:

$$\text{Shape retention ratio (\%)} = \varepsilon_u \times 100 / \varepsilon_m \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Shape recovery ratio (\%)} = (\varepsilon_m - \varepsilon_p) \times 100 / \varepsilon_m \quad (2)$$

Where ε_u is the retention strain at 25°C and ε_p is the recovery strain at 70°C.

For measurement of the recovery stress, the test procedure was similar to the mentioned above (1)~(3), the difference was the last step, (4) the specimen was clamped again with its length fixed and then was heated until 70°C, and the tensile stress was recorded as the recovery stress.

2.7 Antibacterial properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

The anti-bacterial properties of g-GO and g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites were tested against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) as negative bacteria models. *E. coli* (*E. coli*, ATCC® 25922TM) were purchased from ATCC (American Type Culture Collection) and used according to established safety protocols. Luria broth base (LB broth, Cat. #: 12795-027) and select agar (Cat. #: 30391-023) used for *E. coli* culture were purchased from Lablead. *E. coli* mono-colonies was incubated in LB broth at 37°C on an orbital shaker overnight and the obtained bacteria suspensions were diluted into desired concentrations prior to use. GO, g-GO, g-GO/PLLA, PLCL were immersed in 4 mL of liquid medium and 20 uL of *E. coli* mixed solution, respectively. Then, incubated with constant orbital shaker at 37°C for 24 hours. After that, the diluted medium was casted on agar plate for colony counting. Pure bacteria growth broth was also tested and served as a negative control.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Characterization of g-GO

In order to improve the dispersibility of graphene oxide in organic solvents, PLLA is grafted to the surface of GO through solution polymerization of L-lactic acid. The FTIR spectra of GO and g-GO are displayed in Figure 1. The strong absorption peak appeared at 3433 cm^{-1} is ascribed to asymmetric stretching vibration of -OH. The absorption peak at a wavenumber of 1628 cm^{-1} belongs to a vibration absorption peak of C=C. The absorption peak at 1091 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching vibration peak of C-O-C. Meanwhile, the peaks present at about 1730 cm^{-1} and 1752 cm^{-1} in the spectra of g-GO is assigned to the vibration absorption peak of C=O of ester group, which indicates that PLLA chains were successfully grafted onto the surface of GO.

Figure 1 FTIR spectra of GO and g-GO

3.2 Characterization of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

Figure 2 shows the FTIR spectra of g-GO, PLLA and g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites with different composition. As we can see, there are no obvious differences between the FTIR spectra of pure PLLA and g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites. The vibrational absorption peak corresponding to the ester group of PLLA is almost at the wavelength of 1749.14cm⁻¹. In addition, no absorption peak at 3436 cm⁻¹ was observed in the infrared spectrum of the g-GO/PLLA composite material, and this absorption peak corresponds to the stretching vibration peak of hydroxyl (-OH) on the surface of g-GO. It may be that there is a hydrogen bond between the hydroxyl group (-OH) in g-GO and C=O in the PLLA molecular chain leading to this change, but the hydrogen bonding effect is weak. So we can draw a corollary: When g-GO/PLLA composites were prepared by solution blending, there was no chemical reaction between g-GO and PLLA in the mixed solution, but mechanical mixing.

Figure 2 FTIR spectra of PLLA, g-GO and g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites.

DSC heating curves of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites with different composition are presented in Figure 3. Their main thermal characteristics are summarized on Table 1. It can be seen that all samples exhibit a melting peak at around 168 °C corresponding to melting of PLLA crystalline. According to the result of Table 1, the T_m values of the nanocomposites are a little higher than that of neat PLLA. It also can be seen from Table 1, the crystallinity of PLLA in the nanocomposites decreases with the increase of the g-GO content, which should be attributed to the imperfect crystalline of PLLA domain. The addition of g-GO hinders the ordered arrangement of PLLA chains during crystallizing process.

Figure 3 DSC heating curves for g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites.

Table 1 Thermal properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

Sample Number	T _g (°C)	T _m (°C)	ΔH _m (J/g)	Crystallinity(%)
PLLA	56.47	166.42	39.22	42.13
0.5wt%g-GO/PLLA	57.88	167.12	36.77	39.51
1.0wt%g-GO/PLLA	56.84	167.13	35.44	38.07
2.0wt%g-GO/PLLA	56.84	169.89	34.51	37.07

To characterize the dispersity of g-GO in the nanocomposites, SEM images of fracture surfaces of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites were examined, as displayed in Figure 4. The gray part of the figure is the PLLA matrix. The brittle fracture surface of the PLLA is smooth and with the increase of the g-GO content, the fracture surface become rough. It can be observed that the g-GO are evenly distributed on the PLLA matrix, as shown in Figure 4 (b). In Figure 4 (c), there are a small amount of g-GOs agglomerated into graphite flakes. However, the g-GO agglomerations (white spots) can be observed evidently when the g-GO content is 2wt%, as shown in Figure 4 (d).

Figure 4 The SEM micrography of fracture surface for (a) PLLA, (b) (0.5wt%) g-GO/PLLA, (c) (1wt%) g-GO/PLLA, (d) (2wt%) g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

3.3 Mechanical properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

Figure 5 shows the typical stress-strain curves of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites at room temperature. The stress-strain curves of the nanocomposites show a yielding behavior. As continuing to stretch the sample, the stress rises slowly at a very small rate, and strain hardening occurs until the sample is broken. At the same time, it can be seen that the addition of g-GO has a very significant effect on the mechanical properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites, and the detailed data is listed in Table 2.

Fig. 5 Stress-strain curves of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites at room temperature

Sample Number	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
PLLA	12.38±0.42	35.23±1.32	178.61±10.23
0.5wt%g-GO/PLLA	17.14±0.61	35.74±2.45	108.98±6.65
1.0wt%g-GO/PLLA	18.57±0.39	37.07±2.23	62.64±7.21
2.0wt%g-GO/PLLA	10.38±0.32	33.43±1.78	34.51±3.21

It can be seen from the Table 2 that the elastic modulus and tensile strength of the nanocomposites initially increase with the increase of g-GO content and show the maximum at 1wt% g-GO loading. Further increasing the g-GO content leads to reduction in elastic modulus and tensile strength. However, elongation at break of the nanocomposite keeps constant decrease with the increase of g-GO content. The reasons for above mentioned phenomena can be explained as follows: On the one hand, the mechanical strength of g-GO is very high. Therefore, according to the composite law, the higher g-GO content, the better the mechanical strength of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites. On the other hand, as the content of g-GO increases, the crystallinity of the nanocomposites decreases result in the decrease of mechanical strength. Moreover, when the content of g-GO is high, it will reunion in the nanocomposite material, which can be considered as a defect in the nanocomposites leading to the decrease of mechanical properties for g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites. The combination of these factors can illuminate the trend of the mechanical properties varying with the g-GO loading.

3.4 Shape memory properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

The (1.0wt%)g-GO/PLLA nanocomposite is used as an example to demonstrate the shape memory effect of the nanocomposites. First, the sample with slender strips is deformed to spiral shape at 70°C followed cooling the sample to room temperature and removing the force applied to the sample after 10 minutes. Then, the sample is reheated to 70°C, it can be seen that the sample recovers its original shape in a very short time, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Photographs showing the shape memory effect of (1wt%)g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites (recovery at 70°C) (a) t = 0s (b) t = 2s (c) t = 5s (d) t = 10s (e) t = 15s (f) t = 30s

In order to further investigate the effect of g-GO content on the shape memory effect of the nanocomposites, the shape retention ratio and shape recovery ratio of different nanocomposites are studied by tensile test. Figure 7 demonstrates the effects of g-GO content on the shape recovery ratio and shape retention ratio for the nanocomposites. It can be seen that the shape recovery ratio and shape retention ratio decrease slightly with the increase of g-GO content. The shape retention ratio of all samples exceeds 90% and the shape recovery ratio decrease from 88% to 76% when the g-GO content increase from 0wt% to 2wt%. In the g-GO/PLLA nanocomposite system, the fixed phase is the crystalline phase in the PLLA matrix, and the reversible phase is the amorphous phase in the PLLA

matrix. According to the DSC test results, the crystallinity of the g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites decreases slightly with g-GO content increasing, which means that the fixed phase decrease. At the same time, the g-GO is equivalent to the impurity particles in the matrix, which can hinder the sliding and recovery of the molecular chains in the material. Therefore, the addition of g-GO reduces the shape memory effect of the nanocomposites to some extent. The results are similar to those in the references [12,13].

Figure 7 Effect of g-GO content on shape retention ratio and shape recovery ratio of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites.

3.5 Antibacterial properties of g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites

The antibacterial performance of the g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites against *E. coli* is evaluated, as shown in Figure 8. For comparison purpose, the results of GO against *E. coli* are also shown in this figure. As can be seen, the GO has good antibacterial property, and the inhibition rate can reach 71%. Although the g-GO has more colonies on the agar plate than the unmodified GO, it still has a good antibacterial effect, and the inhibition rate is up to 50%. The (1wt%)g-GO/PLLA nanocomposite has obvious antibacterial effect compared to pure PLLA.

Figure 8 Bacterial colonies formed on LB-agar plates were treated with different samples: (a) Blank sample, (b)with GO, (c)with g-GO, (d)with (1wt%)g-GO/PLLA nanocomposite

4 CONCLUSIONS

The GO is modified by lactic acid solution polymerization and the dispersion of g-GO in dichloromethane is improved. The addition of g-GO decrease the crystallinity of the nanocomposites

to some extent. With the g-GO content increasing, the elastic modulus and tensile strength increase and reaches the maximum when the g-GO content is 1wt% while the elongation at break decreases. Although the shape recovery ratio and shape retention ratio of the nanocomposites reduce with the addition of g-GO, the g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites shows good shape memory effect with shape retention ratio and shape recovery ratio exceed 90% and 80%, respectively. The g-GO/PLLA nanocomposites show antibacterial effect to some extent. The novelty of these nanocomposites is due to the combination of shape memory properties, mechanical properties and antibacterial properties. Thus, these multifunctional nanocomposites have great potential in minimally invasive applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Kuang, F. Chen, L. Chang L, Facile preparation of open-cellular porous poly (L-lactic acid) scaffold by supercritical carbon dioxide foaming for potential tissue engineering applications, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, **307**, 2017, pp. 1017-1025
- [2] I.L. Jin, S.I. Kim, S.H. Kim, Lotus-leaf-like structured heparin-conjugated poly(L-lactide-co- ϵ -caprolactone) as a blood compatible material, *Colloids & Surfaces B Biointerfaces*, **103**, 2013, pp. 463-467
- [3] B. Liu, F. Xu, M.Y. Guo, Electrospun PLLA fibers coated with chitosan/heparin for scaffold of vascular tissue engineering, *Surface & Coatings Technology*, **228**, 2013, pp. S568-S573
- [4] Y.S. Wong, S.S. Venkatraman, Recovery as a measure of oriented crystalline structure in poly(L-lactide) used as shape memory polymer, *Acta Materialia*, **58**, 2010, pp. 49-58
- [5] X.L. Lu, W. Cai, Z.Y. Gao, W.J. Tang, Shape memory effects of poly(L-lactides) and its copolymers with poly(ϵ -caprolactone), *Polymer Bulletin*, **58**, 2007, pp. 381-391
- [6] C.F. Kuan, H.C. Kuan, C.C. M, C.H. Chen, Mechanical and electrical properties of multi-wall carbon nanotube/poly(lactic acid) composites, *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, **69**, 2008, pp. 1395-1398
- [7] W.X. Li, Z.W. Xu, L. Chen, M.J. Shan, X. Tian, C.Y. Yang, H.M. Lv, X.M. Qian, A facile method to produce graphene oxide-g-poly(L-lactic acid) as an promising reinforcement for PLLA nanocomposites, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, **237**, 2014, pp. 291-299
- [8] J.A. Tyson, D.G. Calatayud, V. Mirabello, Labeling of graphene, graphene oxides, and of their congeners: imaging and biosensing applications of relevance to cancer theranostics, *Advances in Inorganic Chemistry*, 2016, pp. 397-440
- [9] H. Luo, H. Ao, G. Li, Bacterial cellulose/graphene oxide nanocomposite as a novel drug delivery system, *Current Applied Physics*, **17**, 2016, pp. 32-41
- [10] Y. Liu, J. Wen, Y. Gao, Antibacterial graphene oxide coatings on polymer substrate, *Applied Surface Science*, **436**, 2018, pp. 624-630
- [11] X.L. Lu, W. Cai, Z.Y. Gao, Shape-memory behaviors of biodegradable poly(L-lactide-co- ϵ -caprolactone) copolymers, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **108**, 2008, pp. 1109-1115
- [12] F. Pilatea, A. Toncheva, P. Dubois, J.M. Raquez, Shape-memory polymers for multiple applications in the materials world, *European Polymer Journal*, **80**, 2016, pp. 268-294
- [13] B.B. Yan, S.Y. Gu, Y.H. Zhang, Polylactide-based thermoplastic shape memory polymer nanocomposites, *European Polymer Journal*, **49**, 2013, pp. 366-378